

Developing a simple digital twin of red *Noctiluca scintillans*

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1. Review

1.1 Introduction

Noctiluca scintillans is a large, enigmatic, ubiquitous, globally distributed predatory dinoflagellate (Hallegraeff *et al.* 2019). Older reports make reference to an alternative name, *N. miliaris*. It ranges in size between 200 and 1000 μm in diameter. Unlike most dinoflagellates, *N. scintillans* lacks a mode of rapid motility; its movement is primarily via altering its buoyancy, sinking when satiated and rising when lacking food (Uhlir & Sahling 1990). For feeding, rather than actively hunting its prey, it uses a sticky tentacle and mucus to feed on particles that drift or swim into reach (Nawata & Sibaoka 1983).

Two forms of the *Noctiluca scintillans* have been observed:

- (i) the purely predatory form (in which it is recorded as a protist- or micro- zooplankton), is a translucent pale pink in colour; these are hereafter referred to as red *Noctiluca*.
- (ii) the mixoplanktonic green *Noctiluca*, so called because of their green colouration from the community of phototrophic prasinophytes (*Pedinomonas noctilucae*) which they host as symbionts (Sweeney 1971, 1978). Green *Noctiluca* is also a predator, but its symbionts provide it with another means to acquire energy in the absence of prey.

While red *Noctiluca* is cosmopolitan, occurring in temperate to sub-tropical coastal regions, green *Noctiluca* blooms only in warmer tropical waters (Harrison *et al.* 2011).

The enigmatic status of *Noctiluca*, Latin for 'night light', and the feature that most draws blooms of this organism to public attention, relates to its phosphorescence. This appears when it is disturbed (as in crashing waves on a beach, boat wakes, etc.), hence the species name *scintillans*, and its common name 'sea sparkle'. The bioluminescence capacity decreases during prolonged starvation, linking this energy expense process to the dinoflagellate's nutritional status (Buskey *et al.* 1992; Buskey 1995).

1.1.1 Aim of this review

This review focuses on red *Noctiluca scintillans* due to their presence and ability to form blooms in UK coastal and marine waters (Harrison *et al.* 2011). Green *Noctiluca* has not yet been recorded off the UK. The findings from this review inform the development of a simple digital twin of red *Noctiluca*, as reported in Section 2 and in its allied operation manual (Mitra 2025).

From here on, unless otherwise noted, 'Noctiluca' refers specifically to the red form.

1.2 *Noctiluca* and Harmful Algal Blooms (HABs)

Because of the pink-red colouration of surface slicks of *Noctiluca*, which align with the appearance of archetypal 'red-tides', *Noctiluca* is often considered as harmful. However, *Noctiluca scintillans* is not listed as a Harmful Algal Bloom (HAB) species in the IOC-UNESCO Taxonomic Reference List of Harmful Micro Algae (Lundholm *et al.* 2009). Nonetheless, dense blooms of *Noctiluca* are

associated with damage to fisheries and aquaculture; for example, in Tasmania *Noctiluca* blooms have been perceived to be a threat to local aquaculture salmon industry (Marshall 2004).

1.2.1 Ammonia/ammonium content and links to ecosystem damage

A reason that *Noctiluca* may be considered as a harmful species (e.g., see Smayda 1997) is because the cells become loaded with very high concentrations of ammonia (NH₃) and ammonium (NH₄⁺) (Okaichi & Nishio 1976). The level of unionised ammonia within a cell can vary over an order of magnitude, from ca. 0.04 to 0.4 µg cell⁻¹ (Hallegraeff *et al.* 2019), with higher levels in starved cells. While that content may be a deterrent to predators, the potential releases into the water column have given more cause for concern. Hallegraeff *et al.* (2019) collated data indicating NH₃+NH₄⁺ levels ranging from ca. 5-150 µg L⁻¹ for blooms of 100-300 cells L⁻¹ to as high as ca. 2000 µg L⁻¹ in slicks of 2000 cells L⁻¹. In nature, however, there are various factors that will affect this relationship, including consumption of ammonia/ammonium by microalgal prey; the removal of those prey enables a net accumulation of the nutrient in the water column. A rapid release of ammonia/ammonium from decaying animals (fish, crabs etc.), which may have died due to other interactions such as a lack of food following the predatory activity of large *Noctiluca* blooms, and also with deoxygenation events associated with *Noctiluca* activity and death, may also harm ecosystems. Examples of such events have been reported from the North China Sea (Wang *et al.* 2023), western and eastern coastal waters of India (Padmakumar *et al.* 2010, Baliarsingh *et al.* 2016), and are often linked to eutrophication creating large phytoplankton and mixoplankton blooms stimulating *Noctiluca* growth. In these contexts, *Noctiluca* can be seen as a symptom of ecosystem damage (i.e. eutrophication) as much, or rather than, as a causative agent itself.

1.2.2 Direct food web interactions

Noctiluca are voracious feeders and have a diverse diet ranging from phytoplankton to copepods and fish eggs (Kimor 1979; Nakamura 1998). Its mode of feeding, using mucus to ensnare potential food items, results in dense populations of the dinoflagellate stripping the water column of other organisms. It is particularly effective at removing diatoms (Huang & Qi 1997; Fonda-Umani *et al.* 2004; Harrison *et al.* 2011), while being less effective against smaller phytoplankton and mixoplankton (see subsection, '1.3.5 Mode of predation', below). In consequence, *Noctiluca* competes with copepods not only by removal of their eggs (Cabal *et al.* 2008; Quevedo *et al.* 1999), but also in removal of food for adult copepods. The threat to ecosystems indicated by *Noctiluca* blooms is thus a combination of the eutrophic conditions that promote growths of prey which then feed the dinoflagellate and a disruption of the food chain. *Noctiluca* thus appears as an Ecosystem Disruptive Algal Bloom (EDAB, Sunda *et al.* 2006) species, rather than a HAB species. Potentially deleterious blooms only last for a short period (until exhaustion of prey).

The development of dense populations of *Noctiluca* are thus critically dependent upon the growth of dense populations of potential prey (Sriwoon *et al.* 2008). This leads to a potential linkage of increasing blooming events with the eutrophication that promotes microalgal (phytoplankton, mixoplankton) growth (Porumb 1992). Importantly, however, factors other than prey availability also impact *Noctiluca* growth, the relative importance of which probably changes according to the locality, phase of bloom formation, and environmental conditions (Furuya *et al.* 2006; Elbrächter & Qi 1998).

It has been suggested that *Noctiluca* predate on potential HAB dinoflagellates or their cysts (Drifts *et al.* 2013), and even to translocate toxins from such species (Escalera *et al.* 2007 but see Frangopulos *et al.* 2011). There are contrasting reports on whether *Noctiluca* grazes on toxic dinoflagellates (Garrido *et al.* 2023) or whether they are killed by such plankton (Hallegraeff *et al.* 2019). This conflict may relate to differences in the toxin content of the prey, to the make up of the total diet, and also the physiological state of the prey as well as the *Noctiluca* (whether laboratory grown or taken from the natural environment).

Another impact of *Noctiluca* upon the ecosystem is the regeneration of nutrients. Predation inevitably results in the release of organic (Zhang *et al.* 2017) and inorganic wastes (Okaichi & Nishio 1976; Montani *et al.* 1998; Ara *et al.* 2013). The rate and form of releases will depend on prey stoichiometry and satiation, and thence there will be both qualitative and quantitative effects of prey availability (Zhang *et al.* 2017).

1.3 *Noctiluca* bloom formation

Harrison *et al.* (2011) provided a survey of recurrent *Noctiluca* bloom biogeography. Of specific relevance to UK interests are the studies conducted in the German Bight (Uhlig & Sahling 1990; Fock & Greve 2002). Perhaps related to its essentially passive (rather than raptorial) mode of feeding, *Noctiluca* grows best in high nutrient conditions, either at upwelling or in eutrophic zones.

The pink colouration has been suggested as being due to accumulation of pigments from its prey (Balch & Haxo 1984). However, most of the *Noctiluca* cell is translucent except for food vacuoles, which tend to be green-brown. In consequence, *Noctiluca* cells may not be particularly apparent in the water column until the prey are all but consumed. Maximum cell abundance, excepting wind-driven slick, is typically in the region of 1000 L⁻¹.

There are various schools of thought about the causes of red *Noctiluca* blooms, and there are no clear environmental indicators. The definition of 'bloom' is itself problematic as *Noctiluca* performs vertical migration and is typically only apparent when (if) it forms surface slicks. Wind conditions and water movement aid concentration of bloom leading to red tides (Hallegraeff *et al.* 2019). However, to get to that stage, *Noctiluca* must be proliferating for many weeks from initial low cell densities.

One of the most comprehensive descriptions of the formation of *Noctiluca* blooms is given by Uhlig & Sahling (1990), specifically considering growths off Helgoland in the North Sea. This may be considered as particularly relevant to UK waters, although it should be noted that with climate change, and modifications to the eutrophication status of the North Sea over the last 30 years, current day growth dynamics may be different.

Uhlig & Sahling (1990) suggest that *Noctiluca* growth starts in March/April, with cells initially present lower in the water column. Over the following months, cells become increasingly more obvious as they gradually rise up through the water column. The bloom always collapses in August. The cause for this seems to be that *Noctiluca* cells in the surface waters appeared to be irreversibly damaged; this is presumably due to exposure to UV sunlight and/or to elevated temperatures exceeding lethal levels. The damage is sufficient to prevent feeding. In addition, sexual reproduction follows a diurnal pattern; with longer days in summer the cells may be less able to divide. Food digestion results in the cells becoming buoyant and rising through the water column.

Wang *et al.* (2023) documents *Noctiluca* blooms off China between 1933 and 2020. While the number of events have increased over time, the number of days that each event persists is negligible. This is consistent with Uhlig & Sahling (1990), that blooms apparent at the surface are terminal events. This creates a problem because typically (and as in Wang *et al.* 2023) background information such as nutrient concentrations are determined only during that surface bloom. Information for events leading up to the surface event (prey dynamics, for example) are not known.

Bloom development may start near shore and then move off shore but only if high nutrient levels are present to support prey growth (Batistić *et al.* 2018; Kordubel *et al.* 2024). A need for high P-containing prey to support good growth rates (associated with the usual high DNA content of dinoflagellates; Rizzo 2003) was identified by Zhang *et al.* (2020); decreasing P levels in eutrophication may thus be useful in containing the potential for *Noctiluca* blooms (Fonda Umani *et al.* 2004; Oguz & Velikova 2010). However, it should be noted that low P conditions promote toxin production in other dinoflagellates (e.g., John & Flynn 2002).

Because of the cosmopolitan distribution of the organism, evidence of factors affecting the growth of *Noctiluca* comes from many sources; it is assumed that the red *Noctiluca* in UK waters is physiologically similar to populations elsewhere – there are no reasons to suspect otherwise.

The following sections consider various factors promoting *Noctiluca* growth.

1.3.1 Temperature

Noctiluca occurs in waters typically of 10-25 °C (Harrison *et al.* 2011). Hallegraeff *et al.* (2019) collated data for temperatures supporting *Noctiluca* proliferation:

- Sydney (New South Wales, Australia): blooms have been observed in spring and late summer at temperatures of 19-24 °C;
- Tasmanian waters: since 2004 established overwintering *Noctiluca* populations have been observed; these thrive in winter at temperatures of 10-20 °C.

Further Hallegraeff *et al.* (2019) conducted experiments with *Noctiluca* obtained from Tasmanian waters at temperatures 12-25 °C and salinity 20. They reported that growth rates increased with increasing temperatures between 12 and 23 °C. Highest specific growth rates were obtained between 20 °C and 23 °C ($0.47 \pm 0.04 \text{ d}^{-1}$ and $0.47 \pm 0.015 \text{ d}^{-1}$, respectively). Growth rate halved at 12 °C with limited survival at 7 °C and also, at the higher temperature of 25 °C.

1.3.2 Salinity

Noctiluca does not appear to thrive in estuaries and thus does not favour lower salinity (Harrison *et al.* 2011). In their experiments with *Noctiluca* from Tasmanian waters at 17 °C, Hallegraeff *et al.* (2019) found that *Noctiluca* attained the highest specific growth rate ($0.60 \pm 0.06 \text{ d}^{-1}$) at salinity 20. Growth rate decreased with increasing salinity. However, the *Noctiluca* were found to be capable of growing at the growth rate of $0.42 \pm 0.23 \text{ d}^{-1}$ at full salinity of 35 after 28 days of acclimation.

1.3.3 Buoyancy

Although *Noctiluca* cannot swim, it can alter its position in the water column. In addition to actively altering the ionic composition (Elbrächter & Qi 1998), predation leads to production of food vacuoles which in turn results in an increase in the cell weight (Hallegraeff *et al.* 2019); as a result, cells sink. Prey digestion leads to excretion of ammonium which in turn decreases the weight of the *Noctiluca* cells and the starving cells then ascend up the water column (Uhlig & Sahling 1990).

1.3.4 Prey

Noctiluca scintillans has been cultured in the laboratory on small phytoflagellates (Sweeney 1963; Eckert & Reynolds 1967; Uhlig & Sahling 1982) and axenically using glucose adsorbed on diatomaceous earth (McGinn 1971). Although it has been reported to consume a wide variety of items, including phytoplankton, mixoplankton, zooplankton, larval fish (Enomoto 1956; Raghu Prasad 1958; Kimor 1979), in other instances clear evidence of the consumption of zooplankton or fish eggs is lacking despite an otherwise indiscriminate feeding action (Hallegraeff *et al.* 2019). In contrast, Zhang *et al.* (2017) suggests a preference, or some level of discrimination, for higher quality food items.

Buskey (1995) conducted experiments to study the effect of changes in food concentration on the growth rate of *Noctiluca*. The study reported that the growth rates were dependent on prey type. For example, *Noctiluca* attained moderate growth rates (0.15-0.19 d⁻¹) with smaller flagellates (e.g., *Prorocentrum micans*, *Dunaliella tertiolecta*) but growth rates were significantly lower (< 0.1 d⁻¹) with the similar sized *Isochrysis galbana* (zooplankton have been reported to avoid grazing *I. galbana* of low quality, see Mitra & Flynn 2006 and references therein). Highest growth rates (0.29-0.45 d⁻¹) were supported by diatoms and prasinophytes.

Hallegraeff *et al.* (2019) reported results from studies of *Noctiluca* grown on various phytoplankton and mixoplankton with different levels of agitation, temperature and salinities. *Noctiluca* were unable to grow when provided with small non-motile species (such as cyanobacteria *Synechococcus* and mixoplankton *Emiliana*) but grew particularly well on larger mixoplanktonic flagellates. Agitation (which would enhance encounter rates of the prey with the mucus used to entrap it and/or interfere with mucus avoidance by motile prey) was found to enhance growth.

1.3.5 Mode of predation and growth rates

Prey capture by *Noctiluca* exploits mucus produced by the tentacle (Nawata & Sibaoka 1983). Encounter with prey depends on either the prey swimming into the mucus or colliding with the *Noctiluca* cell itself, or (for non-motile prey), for collisions due to relative movements with different levels of buoyancy and/or of turbulence to initiate such contacts.

Hallegraeff *et al.* (2019) reported an ability of *Noctiluca* to grow very slowly (0.05-0.15 d⁻¹) when fed with non-motile pico-phytoplankton (*Synechococcus*; 1-1.5 µm) or non-motile nano-mixoplankton (*Emiliana huxleyii*, 5 µm) and *Gephyrocapsa* (15 µm) and when the cultures were agitated. Growth rates were higher (0.18-0.26 d⁻¹) when *Noctiluca* offered small motile nano-phytoplankton (*Rhodomonas*) and nano-mixoplankton (*Heterosigma akashiwo*) or small diatoms such as *Thalassiosira* and *Chaetoceros*. Interestingly, growth rates were also found to be negatively

impacted by very high prey abundance; good growth rates were obtained when *Noctiluca* were fed with the flagellate *Tetraselmis suecica* (10-15 μm) at abundances of ca. 100-1000 cells mL^{-1} , but death occurred when the *Noctiluca* were presented with > 8000 prey cells mL^{-1} . Whether the death was a function of changes in pH (high pH occurs at high phototroph abundances) is unknown. The highest growth rates (up to 0.69 d^{-1}) were obtained when *Noctiluca* were fed with the mixoplankton dinoflagellate *Gymnodinium catenatum* (37 μm) occurring in short chains of 2-4 cells. The *Noctiluca* cultures survived for 8 months when cultured in a plankton wheel and fed on *G. catenatum* (although high prey concentrations could kill the *Noctiluca* predator).

The type of turbulence has also been reported to affect *Noctiluca* growth (Buskey 1995; Hallegraeff *et al.* 2019). A gentle movement such as that given by a plankton wheel was found to be best, rather than the cultures being stationary or manually shaken.

1.4 *Noctiluca* death and losses via predation

Development of the potential for *Noctiluca* blooms and causes of bloom collapse are important topics.

1.4.1 Death

Studies indicate that *Noctiluca* dies rapidly, within 4 days, of the exclusion of prey (Hallegraeff *et al.* 2019). That situation would likely align with *Noctiluca* cells having risen to the surface where the absence of prey to absorb damaging UV light would also conspire to promote a rapid collapse of the bloom (Uhlig & Sahling 1990). Like all plankton, *Noctiluca* exhibits an optimal temperature regime; death will occur rapidly beyond a certain level (ca. $>25^{\circ}\text{C}$).

1.4.2 Losses due to predation

Noctiluca itself does not appear to have obvious predators other than jellies and adult copepods, although the latter may be negatively impacted by its bioluminescence (Yilmaz *et al.* 2005). Many of the zooplankton that would otherwise provide a link from protist plankton to higher trophic levels may find *Noctiluca* unpalatable or of poor nutritional value due to a combination of the high ammonia/ammonium levels and low C-density (i.e., low C per biovolume; Menden-Deuer & Lessard 2000).

The most effective grazers are most likely gelatinous zooplankton (e.g., cnidarians, ctenophores, salps), not least because these metazoan zooplankton grow rapidly and are often highly effective as indiscriminate feeders (Batistić *et al.* 2018; Stone & Steinberg 2016).

1.5 Summary to support digital twin construction

1.5.1 Abiotic conditions

Seasonality, day-length and cloudiness: These interact via the availability of light that promotes primary production, which then supports *Noctiluca* bloom development, and promotion of *Noctiluca* death at the termination of the bloom day length.

Mixed Layer Depth (MLD): The MLD, together with factors affecting surface light, affects the light regime within the water column, impacting primary production and thence prey growth for *Noctiluca*. In addition, because of the way that *Noctiluca* blooms develop, the greater the MLD the greater is the depth-integrated prey availability.

Nutrients: The nutrient load affects the ability of the phytoplankton prey to attain a given level of abundance. The nutrient load interacts with the MLD to describe the total depth-integrated prey availability. There are interactions between seasonality MLD and nutrient load; collectively the growing phytoplankton biomass self-shades and limits its own growth rate and extent. Because of the general non-discriminatory nature of *Noctiluca* feeding, only a generalised prey field is considered here, and accordingly the nutrient type is limited to N (as nitrate and ammonium).

1.5.2 General biotic conditions

Prey type: Because of the general non-discriminatory nature of *Noctiluca* feeding, only a generalised prey field is considered here. The prey are explicitly described as phytoplankton, though osmotrophy is not considered here.

Prey stoichiometry: The microalgal prey types is described in terms of variable C:N:Chl stoichiometry. This is required as prey quality affects *Noctiluca* growth and also nutrient regeneration. The nutrient status, and the availability of light (both in consequence of light at the surface and also light-attenuation due to microalgal growth throughout the MLD), together affect photoacclimation and thence Chl:C.

Chlorophyll (Chl): In recognition of the use of Chl as a proxy for phytoplankton+mixoplankton biomass, and also because of the need to consider photoacclimation with nutrient-stress (with impacts on Chl:C), Chl is needed as a model output.

Growth physiology: The model needs to describe light-nitrate-ammonium interactions in order to capture the impacts of eutrophication and ammonium regeneration by the *Noctiluca*. The maximum growth rate of the prey is set at 1.4 d^{-1} , but varies with temperature according to a general Q_{10} formulation. This is to reflect an assumption that different prey will be available seasonally.

Predation on *Noctiluca*: *Noctiluca* blooms only develop in the absence of effective predation. While undoubtedly there is scope for various interactions with copepods (*Noctiluca* eating copepod eggs, while the adults of large copepod species may eat *Noctiluca*), these interactions are considered too complex and too poorly defined to make at this time.

1.5.3 *Noctiluca* physiology

Temperature, salinity and pH interactions: Evidence points to a temperature-response curve with an optimum (de facto maximum) temperature of ca. 23 °C, with a sharp decline (death) after this value. That *Noctiluca* grows in the winter at ca. 10 °C suggests that the lower extreme is more in keeping with a tapering response rather than a sudden drop-off. Salinity data suggest a need to only consider full salinity (no salinity variable is needed). There appears to be no information on the effects of pH changes, either during primary production or with ocean acidification. However, the observation in Hallegraeff *et al.* (2019) that *Noctiluca* cells were killed in the presence of high prey abundances could flag a sensitivity to high pH that would develop during large microalgal blooms (e.g., Flynn & Mitra 2023a). Accordingly, only the impact of temperature is considered here.

Maximum growth rate: The maximum growth rate (noting that this is temperature sensitive), appears to be in the region of a division per day (0.693 d⁻¹).

Death rate: Death results from starving (4 d of starvation being lethal, though this would likely depend on the rate at which prey were exhausted and the nutritional state of the prey), and also when exposed to high light at the surface. Both mechanisms likely function in reality, in part because the lack of prey would also leave the water column sufficiently clear such that UV penetration would be greater.

Buoyancy: *Noctiluca* ascends and descends in response to satiation. Evidence points to the organism moving up through the water column as it exploits the prey field.

Stoichiometry: As there is no evidence that *Noctiluca* has a markedly variable elemental stoichiometry, it is assumed here to be fixed.

2. The Digital Twin Simulator

A digital twin is a simulation model that provides a description of a real-life process with all the pertinent details and interactions reproduced in accordance with expectations.

This *Noctiluca* digital twin provides a description that draws together evidence from the literature (Section 1). It must be stressed that the literature evidence lacks various objective levels of detail. For example, experiments lack measurements of C,N,cell stoichiometry, predation rates, migration rates etc. This problem is common to plankton science (Flynn *et al.* 2022). However, there are much data to support an expert witness validation (Turing test) approach, in which the guiding principle is that the model should behave and have a conceptual basis that accords with the information that does exist.

2.1 The red *Noctiluca* simulator framework

The red *Noctiluca* simulator (Fig.1) describes processes within a 1-D water column. The total mixed layer depth (MLD) is divided into 1 m depths with vertical eddy diffusion between the blocks and across the ergocline (which for applications to red *Noctiluca* blooms would be a thermocline); the latter describes movements into and out of the lowest block of the mixed layer depth. The mixed layer depth can be altered to represent nearshore (e.g., 5 m) to offshore (e.g., 30-50 m) coastal waters. The 1D water column model description follows that of Flynn & Fasham (2002).

Figure 1. Schematic of the red *Noctiluca* simulator. The phytoplankton utilize dissolved inorganic nutrients (DI-Nut) and light for growth via phototrophy. A percentage of the dissolved organic photosynthate (DOM) is lost through leakage. Growth of red *Noctiluca* is via prey consumption. Inefficiencies in digestion leads to voiding of undigested organic material (VOM) and release of excretory products. VOM is assumed to be broken down by bacteria (not explicitly described here) and thence contributes to the dissolved inorganic pool (DI-Nut).

The red *Noctiluca* simulator (**Fig.1**), comprises the following components:

- three pools of dissolved inorganic nutrients (DI_{Nut}) representing nitrate (NO_3^-), ammonium (NH_4^+) and dissolved carbon dioxide (CO_2) described as:

$$\frac{d}{dt}DI_{Nut} = excretion_{phyto+Noc} - photosynthesis_{phyto}$$

where, excretion = release of CO_2 (via respiration) or NH_4^+ (via regeneration).

- red *Noctiluca*: biomass-based dual currency (carbon and nitrogen), variable stoichiometric system dynamics sub-model described as:

$$\frac{d}{dt}Noctiluca = predation - voiding_{VOM} - respiration_{CO_2} - regeneration_{NH_4^+} - death$$

- phytoplankton: biomass-based triple currency (carbon, nitrogen and chlorophyll), variable stoichiometric system dynamics sub-model described as:

$$\frac{d}{dt}phytoplankton = photosynthesis - respiration_{CO_2} - predation - leakage_{DOC}$$

- pools of dissolved organic matter (DOM) and voided organic matter (VOM) for carbon and nitrogen, respectively.

2.2 Red *Noctiluca* sub-model

The red *Noctiluca scintillans* sub-model was configured as a dual currency (carbon and nitrogen) protist zooplankton (**Fig.2**). The core structure was based on the model of Mitra (2006) which is a variable stoichiometric multi-currency eco-physiological model. Predation including prey encounter, capture and ingestion was described following the satiation-controlled encounter-based model of Flynn & Mitra (2016). Metabolic activities associated with anabolism (assimilation and growth) and catabolism (maintenance) leads to regeneration of stoichiometric excesses through specific dynamic action (SDA; McCue 2006). SDA in zooplankton is known to contribute to the loss of around 30% of the assimilated biomass (i.e., biomass that is not voided), in the forms of CO_2 (through respiration) and ammonium (NH_4^+ through excretion). Death was described as a function of starvation and UV damage.

According to the findings of Hallegraeff et al. (2019), the red *Noctiluca* have been configured to sink when satiated following predation. Following digestion, the buoyancy of the *Noctiluca* changes leading to ascension through the water column.

Figure 2. Schematic of red *Noctiluca* cell. *Noctiluca* obtains nourishment via ingestion of prey (phagotrophy). Inefficiencies in digestion results in voiding of faecal material (VOM). Growth (anabolism) and maintenance of the cell (catabolism) leads to losses through respiration (CO_2), excretion (NH_4^+).

2.3 Phytoplankton sub-model

The prey phytoplankton sub-model (**Fig.3**) was described following the C:N:Chl variable stoichiometric model of Flynn & Mitra (2023b). The phytoplankton were configured to uptake dissolved inorganic nutrients (DI_{Nut}) in forms of nitrate (NO_3^-), ammonium (NH_4^+) and dissolved carbon dioxide (CO_2) to drive phototrophy for growth (anabolism). Any inorganics released through metabolic activities such as for cell maintenance (catabolism) were internally recycled to drive phototrophy. A proportion of photosynthate (5-10%) were leaked as dissolved organics (Flynn et al. 2008).

Figure 3. Schematic of phytoplankton sub-model. Phytoplankton uptakes dissolved inorganic nutrients – nitrate (NO_3^-), ammonium (NH_4^+), carbon dioxide (CO_2) and light for growth (anabolism) via phototrophy. Any inorganics released from breakdown of metabolites for cell maintenance (i.e., catabolism) is utilized internally to drive phototrophy. A percentage of the photosynthate (DOM) is lost through leakage. Any CO_2 from catabolism not used for photosynthesis is respired out.

2.4 Abiotic variables

Abiotic variables described in the model are as follows:

- **Latitude:** this allows for geolocating the simulator within the range of UK waters.
- **Mixed Layer Depth:** this allows for selection of a wide-range of water column depths, at 1 m depth intervals, according to location from near-shore (5 m depth) to off-shore coastal (50 m depth) waters. Note: this cannot be changed during the simulation.
- **Attenuation of light in the water column:** this enables the configuration of the attenuation of light in the water column due to presence of coloured dissolved organic matter (cDOM).
- **Date:** this allows for starting the simulation at a given time of year. This function also makes use of the selected latitude.
- **Cloud:** this enables the configuration of the level of obscuration of light by cloud ranging from a clear day with no mist to a heavily overcast sky.
- **Temperature:** this allows the user to choose from a wide range of input options.
- **Sub-mixed layer nutrients:** these are as nitrate and ammonium; these same values are loaded into the mixed layer at the start of the simulation.

2.5 Operating the simulator

The file name of the simulator is: [redNoctiluca_Simulator.sip](#)

This is operated with a free-to-end-user Windows PC application **Powersim Cockpit**. This application enables the user to run model projects that have been developed using Powersim Studio Premium.

Powersim Cockpit only works on the MS Windows OS.

To download Powersim Cockpit, visit <https://powersim.com/download-cockpit/>

IMPORTANT

If you already have any other Powersim Studio product installed, do NOT install Cockpit!

Once downloaded, follow the instructions provided by Powersim to install the software.

Note that the modelling software makes intensive demands of your PC's CPU. Depending on the power of your PC, modelling can affect (slow) the operation of other applications that you may be running, and vice versa.

Best results (i.e., the shortest run time) will be obtained using a PC with multiple cores (i7 and upwards) and having more and faster RAM. Good graphic capabilities are also beneficial.

3. References

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